

TOURISM CITY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: Achievements and shortcomings of Uzbekistan in the field of tourism. Tasks for increasing tourism potential.

Key words: developing industry, development of Uzbekistan, "Sharq Taronalari" international, architectural monuments, economy of our country.

Tourism is a vast and massively developing industry. This sector brings more income to the financial base of developed countries. Among them, it is considered a sector that contributes to the development of Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan has made many achievements in this direction. For example: "Sharq Taronalari" international music festival is also held in Uzbekistan. This also leads to the development of tourism. Tourists come not only to see the festival, but also to see the historical architectural monuments of Uzbekistan. 75% of tourists visiting Uzbekistan visit Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva, and the remaining 25% visit other regions. It can be seen that most of the tourists visit the ancient monuments of Uzbekistan. Currently, most of the developed countries have developed leisure tourism. This direction is not well developed in our country. I think that if we develop this direction, a lot of money will be invested in the economy of our country. In addition, this work will be a good work for our compatriots. Because if they spend the money spent on vacation abroad in our country, it will be of great benefit to the state budget and the wallets of our compatriots.

According to the Sport.uz website, "on March 30, 2023, a number of tasks and assignments were given at the video selector on the development of the country's tourism, which was held under the chairmanship of Shavkat Mirziyoyev. They are:

1. There are many uncertainties in booking road tickets The number of foreign tourists who visited Uzbekistan in 2022 increased 3 times compared to 2021. The export volume of the industry is \$1.6 billion.
2. Subsidy will be given for 25% of the cost of air tickets for new flights. Shortage of domestic flights in air flights. is being built, there is a demand for 350 new wagons for 68 additional trips per week on the railway.
3. Tourist minibus

service will be launched through Kamchik pass. In the field of railway and road transport, 34 electric trains will be purchased by June 1. Tenders will be uploaded and at least 8 will be brought by the end of the year.

4. A new system will be introduced to increase tourism potential." It can be seen that the direction of tourism in Uzbekistan is still developing. Let tourism develop, let our people not get tired of recreation

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